

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15342309

Socio-Economic Factors Influencing Youth Involvement In Rice Agriculture

Epem Ubodiom¹; Moroyei Ebilade²; Yimovie Sakue-Collins³ & Enize Collins-Sakue⁴

¹History Education Department
School of Arts and Social Science
Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education Sgagbama Bayelsa State, Nigeria
Email: V1conscience@gmail.com

²Agricultural Science Education Department
School of Vocational Technology
Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education Sgagbama Bayelsa State, Nigeria
Email: kingstonebi@gmail.com

³Department of Political Science
University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Nigeria; International Doctorial Program in Asia-Pacific Studies,
National Chengchi University, Taiwan
Email: yimovie.sakue@uat.edu.ng

⁴Department of Agricultural Economic, Extension and Rural Development,
Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Even before the arrival of the Europeans into the present day Nigeria, youth have been involved in rice production. Rice is the world's most basic food. Rice will continue to be a staple food in the coming decades, be it in terms of food security, poverty alleviation or youth employment. This paper discusses the socio-economic factors influencing youth involvement in rice agriculture. The paper was premised on primary and secondary sources of information and adopted the multi-disciplinary approach to generate the needed information. This paper revealed that income can influence youths involve in rice participation through purchasing power, access to resources, investment in technologies, risk management and increased productivity. The paper also shows that educational level can influence youths involve in rice participation through awareness and knowledge, adoption of technology, entrepreneurial opportunities, increase productivity, improved decision-making, and innovation and entrepreneurship. This work argues that social networks can influence youths involve in rice participation through information sharing, knowledge transfer, collaboration and partnership, increase adoption, improved decision-making, and empowerment. The paper suggested among others that policy makers and stakeholders in rice production should develop targeted interventions to support youth involvement in rice production, food security, and sustainable rice involvement among youths and that the Government and Non-Governmental Organisation in agriculture should be involve in capacity building of youths by training and retraining them in rice production. This will empower the youths to contribute to sustainable rice production and value chains.

Keywords: Youths' Socio-Economic, Involvement, Rice, Agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

Even before the arrival of the Europeans into the present Nigeria, youth empowerment has long been perceived to be the most thoughtful socio-economic problems confronting Nigeria as a country which has led to increased violent crimes, militancy, restiveness, socially delinquent behaviour and kidnapping. Unemployment has been identified as one of the major causes of social vices, including armed robbery, destitution, prostitution, political thuggery, kidnapping and many more. Youths are also more likely to live in poverty, considering the situation of unemployment among youths. As opined by Beighley (2010) youths continue to face challenges related to unemployment, underemployment and poverty due to poor involvement in agricultural activities such as rice cultivation.

Rice is the world's most basic food. Rice will continue to be a staple food in the coming decades, be it in terms of food security, poverty alleviation, youth employment, use of scarce resources, or impact on the climate. In Nigeria today, rice is ranked first because it has moved from a mere ceremonial to a staple food in most homes as it accounts for about 40% of the total diets of the country's population (Mgbanya, *et al.*, 2019).

Rice cultivation provides several entrepreneurial opportunities for youth not just in Nigeria but all over the world. However, the use of crude implements has been identified as a major constraint to rice cultivation in Nigeria (Mba *et al.*, 2021). This implies that rice production is carried out through physical strength which degenerates as farmers grow older. This has given rise to the aging population of rice farmers making it vital for youths to participate in rice production to close the demand-supply gap in rice production in Nigeria (Alabi *et al.*, 2024). The non-recognition of the need to provide an enabling environment for youth involvement in rice cultivation may be attributed to the absence of suitable information on the factors that influence youth involvement in rice cultivation.

Rice production is viewed as the fulcrum for socio-economic development in Nigeria given that it can facilitate wealth creation through the provision of employment opportunities, ensure food security, provide social stability as well as minimize economic migration from Nigeria. These capacities have however remained unattained notwithstanding several agricultural programmes in Nigeria such as the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), ANCHOR Borrowers among others target the attainment of self-sufficiency in rice production (Arouna *et al.*, 2021). However, Olanrewaju *et al.* (2021) reported that Nigeria is the largest producer of rice in West Africa, it is also the highest importer of the commodity in Africa. Rice importation increased by 4 percent in 2023 as total year import rose from 2.3 in 2022 to 2.4 in 2023 while the area harvested decreased from 3.6 to 3.5 hectares. Rice can be cultivated on irrigated land, rain-fed lowland, upland and deep-water (Izuogu *et al.*, 2023).

Youth is a period of life characterised by vigour, growth, and the transition from childhood to adulthood, commonly defined as the age range between 15 and 40 years. This demography forms a significant portion of the population, especially in developing countries. In African societies, youth make up over 60% of the population, reflecting their vital role in economic and social development (UNFPA, 2014 in Adesina, 2018). In Nigeria, the National Youth Policy defines youth as individuals between the ages of 18 and 35, highlighting their importance as a major source of labour and innovation (Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development, 2019). As stated by Ovwigho and Ifie (2004), the socio-personal definition of youth involves observing individuals in society based on their vibrancy, physical strength, and mental capacity. Youth are viewed as being in the prime of their life, contributing significantly to various sectors, particularly agriculture. The critical role of youth in adopting new agricultural technologies, which are essential for food security and their socio-economic development.

The roles of which youths can play in rice production include a mobilisation tool through which youths' socio-economy can be improved. Buhari *et al.*, (2024) argue that such mobilisation could improve the orientation of the minds of young people by promoting positive attitude towards the worth and dignity in labour. It will also promote the status of farming by giving youths opportunities, profitable enterprises and improving the lot of the community through serviceable projects. Youths' involvement in rice cultivation will, no doubt, go a long way in shaping the developmental heights of the nation, bridged the

increasing chasm of demand and supply of rice in the Nigerian market, and also improves the socio-economic life of the youths (Adesina, 2018).

Some of the limitations that face youth involvement in rice production in Nigeria as observed by Onuk, et al., (2010) include: poor capital base, use of archaic implements, lack of extension contacts, incidence of pests and diseases, lack of improved inputs, bad attitude to farming, education level, income, and social network. In the view of gender inequality, youth's male and female status are very low, they are overwhelmingly more disadvantaged than adult male, and face continuous discrimination. According to Gender Assessment Report in 2015, these inequalities are not only a threat to youth farmers' basic human rights, but also pose a serious threat to the social and economic development of youth farmers (Alabi, et al., 2024).

Concept of Rice

Rice is a cereal grain and in its domesticated form is the staple food of over half of the world's population, particularly in Africa. Rice has become ordinary in many cultures of the world. A considerable amount of the rice produced in developing nations such as Nigeria is lost after harvest through factors such as poor storage and transport. Rice yields can be reduced by pests including insects, rodents, and birds, as well as by weeds, and by diseases such as rice blast. Traditional rice polycultures such as rice-duck farming, and modern integrated pest management seek to control damage from pests in a sustainable way.

As stated by Kawure, et al., (2022) numerous varieties of rice have been raised to improve crop superiority and productivity. Biotechnology has created Green Revolution rice able to produce high yields when supplied with nitrogen fertiliser and managed intensively. Other products are rice able to express human proteins for medicinal use; flood-tolerant or deepwater rice; and drought-tolerant and salt-tolerant varieties. Rice is used as a model organism in biology.

Like all crops, Beighley (2010) observed that rice depends for its growth on both biotic and abiotic environmental factors. The principal biotic factors are crop variety, pests, and plant diseases. Abiotic factors include the soil type, whether lowland or upland, amount of rain or irrigation water, temperature, day length, and intensity of sunlight. Rice grains can be planted directly into the field where they will grow, or seedlings can be grown in a seedbed and transplanted into the field.

As opined by Yuan (2010) rice is the main food staple in Africa, feeding over half the world's population. However, a substantial part of the crop can be lost post-harvest through inefficient transportation, storage, and milling. A quarter of the crop in Nigeria is lost after harvest. Storage losses include damage by mould fungi if the rice is not dried sufficiently.

RESEARCH METHODS

Sources and Method

This study employed the mixed methodology approach. And the sources of data that were collected were; primary and secondary sources and personal observations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Influence of income among youths on rice involvement in Nigeria

The influence of income among youths on their involvement in rice cultivation can be significant. As stated by Mrs. Otenekize Dimiari (2025) during an oral interview youths with higher income may invest in production, adopting modern rice farming techniques and technologies. Ovieme Odeke (2025) added that high income enables rice producers that are youths to access essential resources, such as seeds, fertilizers, equipment, and labour.

According to Mercy Nsirim (2025) youths involved in rice farming with high income can easily invest in modern technologies, such as irrigation systems, precision farming tools, and machinery. Betty Ogbara (2025) further added that high income will help youths involve in rice farming to manage risks, such as crop failures, price fluctuations, and weather-related disasters.

Confidence Igoni Obele (2025) during an oral interview stated that youths involve in rice farming accesses to income will enable them increase their productivity, yields, improve food security and

availability. According to Adevie Ibukilebu (2025) during a personal interview youths involve in rice farming with high income can contribute to economic growth, poverty reduction, and improved livelihoods for youths rice farmers.

Influence of education level among youths on rice participation in Nigeria

The influence education level among youths on their involvement in rice cultivation can be significant. Pamela Joseph (2025) who is an indigene of Agudama-Epie stated during an oral interview that youths with higher education may have better awareness and knowledge about rice involvement, processing, and marketing, enabling them to make informed decisions. Otodiaba Yekwe (2025) during a telephone interview stated that youths with higher education may be more likely to adopt modern rice farming techniques, technologies, and sustainable practices in rice production. According to Utavie Jeremiah (2025) during a personal interview youths with higher education may explore entrepreneurial opportunities in rice value chains, such as processing, marketing, and distributing than those with lower education.

During an oral interview Daddi Ayawari (2025) stated that youths with higher degree or education can easily be involve in rice production, cultivation and value chains. Dr Daddi Ayawari (2025) further stated during an oral interview that youths with higher level of education will easily have skills and knowledge related to rice production and management than youths with lower education such as primary school.

Evarada Abednego (2025) stated during an oral interview that higher educated youths can contribute to increased productivity and efficiency in rice production, then youths with lower education. Evarada Abednego (2025) further stated during an oral interview that youths with higher education can effortlessly make informed decisions about rice production, processing, and marketing. Egba Sinizibe (2025) an indigene of Agbura community during personal interview added that youths with higher education can drive innovation and entrepreneurship in rice value chains, than youths with lower education.

According to respondents such as Mrs. Pamela Joseph (2023), Mr. Adevie Ibukilebu (2023), Mrs. Otodiaba Yekwe (2025) and Dr. Daddi Ayawari (2025) youths that have lower certificated cannot participate in rice production and value chains. But youths with higher level of education can contribute to sustainable rice production and value chains.

Influence of social network among youths on rice participation in Nigeria

Mrs. Biobelemo Ben (2025) made more emphasis by telling the researcher that social networks can facilitate the sharing of information about rice production, processing, and marketing among youths. Mrs. Avah Edward (2025) a widow and an indigene of Igbogene-Epie during a telephone interview with her further stated that social network can influence the transfer of knowledge and skills related to rice production, processing, and marketing.

Mrs. Biobelemo Ben (2025), Mr. Adevie Ibukilebu (2025), Mrs. Osomze Epem (2023) and Dr. Realman Obele Evans (2025) concurred that social network can foster collaboration and partnerships among youths, farmers, and other stakeholders in rice value chain.

A respondent, Dr. Realman Obele Evans (2025), who is an indigene of Agudama-Epie said: social networks can influence youths' attitudes, behaviour, and decisions related to rice production and consumption, and that social networks can facilitate peer-to-peer learning and knowledge sharing among youths. Dr Realman Obele Evans (2025) further stated during the interview that social networks can provide access to resources, such as finance, technology, and markets that can support youths' participation in rice production.

Another respondent, Mrs. Amokiese Ozaka (2023) has this to state; social network can increase the adoption of innovative practices and technologies in rice production among youths. Another respondent, Mr. Adevie Ibukilebu (2025), a youthful dad of 4 kids stated: social networks can provide youths with access to information and knowledge that can inform their decisions about rice production and consumption. Mrs. Biobelemo Ben (2025) further stated that social networks can empower youths to take an active role in rice production and value chains.

According to Tebeda Azibapu (2025) during personal communication limited access to social networks can hinder youths' participation in rice production and value chains, and that social networks can also spread misinformation, which can negatively impact youths' decision and behaviours related to rice productions. Tobibe Epem (2023) during a personal interview acknowledges that the digital divide can exacerbate existing inequalities and limit the potential benefits of social networks for youths in rural areas.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, rice is a cereal grain and in its domesticated form is the staple food of over half of the world's population, particularly in Africa. Rice has become ordinary in many cultures of the world. The involvement of youths in rice production can be influenced by socio-economic factors such as income, educational level, and social networks.

Income can influence youths involve in rice participation through purchasing power, access to resources, investment in technologies, risk management and increased productivity. Educational level can influence youths involve in rice participation through awareness and knowledge, adoption of technology, entrepreneurial opportunities, increase productivity, improved decision-making, and innovation and entrepreneurship. Social networks can influence youths involve in rice participation through information sharing, knowledge transfer, collaboration and partnership, increase adoption, improved decision-making, and empowerment.

Suggestions

The following suggestions were made;

1. Policy makers and stakeholders in rice production should develop targeted interventions to support youth involvement in rice production, food security, and sustainable rice involvement among youths.
2. The Government and Non-Governmental Organisation in agriculture should be involve in capacity building of youths by training and retraining them in rice production. This will empower the youths to contribute to sustainable rice production and value chains.
3. The Government and Non-Governmental Organisation involve in social network production, should up their game so that youths involve in rice production will not hinder from effective information from the social network.
4. The Government agencies and non-State agencies involve in controlling and monitoring social network should up their games so that the social networks will not spread misinformation, which can negatively impact on the decisions of the youth participation in rice production.
5. Youths that are involve in rice production should be allowed easy access to loans and credit facilities. This will curb financial problems and encourage more youths to go into rice cultivation.

REFERENCES

- Adesina, A. (2018). Boosting rice production in Nigeria: Challenges and the way forward. *Nigerian Agricultural Journal*, 49(1), 15-27
- Alabi, D.L, Alao, O. T. & Olagunju, I. B. (2024). Rural households' youth participation in rice agribusiness value chain activities: implications for employment opportunities. *The Journal of Agricultural Sciences - Sri Lanka*, 19(1), 14-30.
- Beighley, D. H. (2010). *Growth and Production of Rice*. In W. H. Verheye, (ed.). Soils, Plant Growth and Crop Production. EOLSS Publishers.
- Buhari, A. K., Muhammad, H. A., Garba, N. & Umar, S. (2024). Risk identification in rice production performance in Kebbi State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Agriculture & Biology Research* 12(1), 1-12.
- Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development. (2019). *National Youth Policy*. file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/DETERMINANTS%20OF%20YOUTHS%E2%80%99%2010-28%20(1).pdf.

- Kawure, S.; Garba, A.A.; Fagam, A.S.; Shuaibu, Y.M.; Sabo, M.U.; Bala, R.A. (2022). Performance of Lowland Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) as Influenced by Combine Effect of Season and Sowing Pattern in Zigau. *Journal of Rice Research and Developments*. 5(2), 16-32.
- Mba, C.L., Madu, A. L., Ajaero, C.K., & Obetta, A. E (2021). Patterns of rice production and yields in South Eastern Nigeria. *African Journal Food Agriculture Nutrition Development*. 21(7), 18330-18348.
- Mgbanya, J. C., Eze, A. V. Amuta, L. A., & Igwe E. O. (2019). *Effect of socioeconomic characteristics of youth farmers on the rice production project in Ishielu Local Government Area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria*. file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/Mgbanya-et-al.pdf
- Ovwigho, B. and Ifie, P. (2004). *The role of youth in rural development*. file:///C:/Users/USER/Downloads/DETERMINANTS%20OF%20YOUTHS%E2%80%99%2010-28%20(1).pdf.
- Yuan, L. (2010). *A scientist's perspective on experience with Sri in China for raising the yields of super hybrid rice*. Cornell University.

Appendix

Primary Sources (Oral Interview)

S/NO	NAME	SEX	AGE	STATUS	DATE
1	Otenekize Dimiari	F	45 Yrs	Rice Farmer	15/1/2025
2	Ovieme Odeke	F	35 Yrs	Youth	15/1/2025
3	Betty Ogbara	F	64 Yrs	Rice Farmer	15/1/2025
4	Igoni Obele	M	52 Yrs	Agric Lecturer	19/1/2025
5	Adevie Ibukilebu	M	48 Yrs	Lecturer	3/2/2025
6	Pamela Joseph	F	54 Yrs	Rice Farmer	5/2/2025
7	Otodiaba Yekwe	F	28 Yrs	Youth	5/2/2025
8	Utavie Jeremiah	M	42 Yrs	Civil Society Practitioner	10/2/2025
9	Didi Ayawari	M	65 Yrs	Agric Lecturer	10/2/2025
10	Evarada Abednego	M	50 Yrs	Rice Farmer	12/2/2025
11	Egba Sinizibe	M	27 Yrs	Youth Leader	24/2/2025
12	Sinizibe Inatimi	M	40 Yrs	Rice Farmer	24/2/2025
13	Biobelemo Ben	F	67 Yrs	Rice Trader	26/2/2025
14	Avah Edward	F	42	Rice Farmer	15/3/2025
15	Realman Obele Evans	M	50 Yrs	Rice Farmer	17/3/2025
16	Tebeda Azibapu	M	22	Youth	19/3/2025
17	Tobibe Epem	M	60 Yrs	Rice Farmer	20/3/2025